

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL STUDY FOR WELDING TECHNOLOGY OF THERMOSET FRP

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Introduction

Back Ground

	Positive	Negative	
	Thermoset (TS) CFRP	Thermoplastic (TP) CFRP	Target
Reliability (Mechanical property)	Cross-linked structure	Non cross-linked structure (Low Creep and Fatigue)	Designed cross-linked structure
Thermal Stability	High	Thermal deformation	High
Prepreg cost	Low	High (Impregnation issue)	Low
Molding time	Cure time issue (Generally long)	Heat & Cool Time (Generally short)	Fast-Cure Technology (Resin, Process)
Molding Conditions	Low Temp. & Pressure	High Temp. & Pressure	Low Temp. & Pressure
Assembly / Bond	Not Weldable (Adhesive / Fastener)	Weldable	Weldable

Concept

- ✓ Laminate structure
Multiple configuration (UD, Fabric etc.)
- ✓ Utilize superior TS CFRP properties
Mechanical, Thermal, Dimensional stability
- ✓ Embedding of TP domain on surface
Design TP domain thickness at micro-scale (μm)
Various TP can be applied
- ✓ Utilize surface TP domain as welding component
Efficient process (Only surface requires heat)
Stable process (Inner TS is stable under heat)

FRP Laminate (after curing) with Weldable surface

There is great focus on Thermoplastic CFRP to improve the productivity. One of motivation is the ease of assembly by welding, then the current trends show developmental interest in bonding technology.

Under proceeding with multi-materials in structural applications, Toray is working on new challenges by incorporating both the superior properties from Thermoset CFRP and the processing benefits from Thermoplastic CFRP.

Experiments

Sample Preparation & Evaluation

- I) Sheet fabrication & Lamination
Fixed CF: T700S (Lab. Trial) Prepreg: T700S/2592 Lamination: [0/90]ns
Cure Condition: 180C, 1hr, 0.5MPa
- II) Welding (Heat Plate Press): 3min, 3MPa
- III) Lap Shear Test: ISO-4587
Tensile speed 2mm/min, CFRP 1mmt
10mm (Bonding length) 45mm (Grip length)
- IV) Cross Peel Test: JASO M406-87
Compression speed 5mm/min, CFRP 2.5mmt

Sample List

No	Pprocess	Bonding Component	Bonding Condition
#1	Welding	Polyamide (PA: Tm215C) 100 μm	240C, 3min
#2		Polypropylene (PP: Tm160C) 100 μm	180C, 3min
#3		Modified Polypropylene (m-PP: Tm160C) 100 μm	180C, 3min
#4	Adhesive	Panel bond 8115@3M (Epoxy) 100 μm	w/ sand blast, 60C, 3hr
#5	(Reference)	MG5000/5038@ETEC (Urethane) 100 μm	w/ sand blast, RT, 3days

Results

Lap Shear Test

Cross Peel Test

Bonding Strength of Lap Shear sample

#1	#2	#3	#4	#5
26.3MPa	3.4MPa	24.9MPa	20.2MPa	9.3MPa
Mixture of adherend and cohesive failure	Delamination from CFRP to PP	Cohesive failure at m-PP	Cohesive failure	Cohesive failure

Numerical Simulations

2D FEM Modeling

- ✓ Tensile / Shear stress analysis
- ✓ 3 longitudinally CFs model
- ✓ Variation of TS/TP position
- ✓ Variation of CF/TP strength

Effect of TS/TP position

Simulation for TP0.5

Influence of CF/TP strength

- ✓ Confirmed material concept by embedding a thermoplastic domain in the thermoset CFRP for a bonded structure
- ✓ Confirmed equivalent bonding strength for thermoplastic embedded thermoset CFRP compared to an adhesively bonded structure
- ✓ 2D Numerical analysis shows the interface between CF and TP domain is an important parameter that governs the bonding strength
- ✓ It is suggested that delamination or debond does not occur at the interface between the TS/TP domain